

DIGITAL DESIGN FOR EARTHEN CONSTRUCTION: A NEW PROCESS FOR NEW SHAPES

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Abstract

The construction and architecture fields are, henceforth, pursuing the goal of sustainability. Raw earth is among the most sustainable materials ever and represents by far one of the earliest building materials. Earthen construction mainly characterizes the antique world with common techniques such as the Adobe, Pisè, Torchis, and Bauges, still un-modified for years: several high-quality contemporary buildings, such as the house in Schlins built by Rauch in Austria and the Boltshauser Architectures, are built with the same pisè technique as the ancient dwellings. However, valuable raw earth features aiding environmental sustainability have fostered a trend toward the updating of earthen construction techniques. Authors such as Rauch and Heringer refer to the 'Upscaling Earth' concept as identifying a potential enhancement for this building system. The world of digital fabrication is contributing to this evolution, and additive manufacturing is opening up new scenarios. Today, several interesting examples of earth-built prototypes are present: they show such material potential also with its limitations mainly related to structural and maintenance-related issues. Digital fabrication can, however, be used in different ways to innovate earthen construction, identifying additive manufacturing as an alternative approach. This paper aims to present an experimental construction experience realized by the FabLab research group at the Polytechnic University of Bari, where 3d printing is used to build experimental moulds that allow the earth into shapes never used before. A description of the 'Wood Beehive' prototype, an organic construction based on the spatial tessellation obtained by the repetition of a single brick shaped as a truncated octahedron, is provided. A method for determining architectural shapes through form-finding has been implemented within an algorithm, identifying a construction system merging the pisè, masonry, and bricks techniques with 3D FDM printing. The entire project was deployed during an experimental workshop conducted in Abruzzo between July and September 2022.

Keywords: digital design, earthen architecture, form finding, optimisation, 3d printing for design, generative design, spatial tasselating

1 BUILDING WITH VISCOUS MIXES, THE MODERN WAY

Earth is one of the oldest building materials. It has been used since ancient times for two reasons: its direct availability in most places where clay sediments are concentrated; and its ease of processing, which makes it a material that can be used by people who are not specialised in building. In fact, it often characterises 'poor' settlements where self-build sites are constructed with the participation of the users who will then use the built spaces.

The history of earthen architecture has left us with traditional building techniques that can be divided into four main categories: adobe, which consists of laying masonry using parallelepipedal bricks formed from raw earth in wooden moulds and then dried; bauge, which consists of laying wet raw earth bricks together to form

thick masonry; pisé, which consists of building with earth pressed under high pressure; and torchis, a technique that puts together wooden frames with raw earth filling the spaces between them.

Raw earth, in all its forms, has always favoured solid shapes, and its natural evolution was the Roman cement conglomerate, on the one hand, and baked clay bricks on the other. The main reasons for this development are to be found in the increased mechanical strength (which isn't significant in either case), but above all in the increased resistance to weathering corrosion phenomena such as rain.

However, both developments are associated with a greater amount of energy being required to produce the building material. The Opus Cementicium needs lime to amalgamate the pozzolan, which needs a combustion process to be produced. Ceramic bricks must also be fired at high temperatures. So, both development processes increase the energy requirement, which is even higher in the case of later Portland concretes. The reconsideration, therefore, of the direct use of raw earth compounds assumes considerable importance today, when the issue of environmental sustainability has become central in any reasoning related to R&D, even in the field of architecture.

This interest increases when we consider the new digital manufacturing techniques that are innovating the construction world, particularly additive manufacturing, which can use viscous composites in its specific application. 3D printing is today one of the most relevant techniques for industrial research in many fields. There are a wide variety of application technologies: the most common is Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM), which uses plastic materials; similarly, the Liquid Deposition Modelling - LDM - technique involves depositing material of a viscous nature through an extruder. The latter is now being used with materials such as concrete mixes in already certified structures, and is also being used experimentally with earth mixes, as in the case of the two prototypes built by Wasp - Gaia in 2018 and Tecla in 2021 - or the experiments carried out by the IAAC in Barcelona.

However, additive manufacturing can also be used indirectly to build using viscous materials such as raw earth. This applies to the so-called "indirect use" to build moulds for fluid materials. Here, too, we have a number of examples of how this system of construction is put into practice.

The HiRes Concrete Slab, developed by ETH Zurich in 2021, is one of the latest experiments: an ultra-efficient structural element that showcases the unique advantages of 3D-printed formwork, including material reduction, integrated construction services and spectacular free-form aesthetics. HiRes Slab is a thin, double-curved slab whose geometry allows the concrete to resist compression forces more efficiently. This greatly reduces the amount of material used. It is made using a combination of digital manufacturing processes and consists of 43 parts that make up the entire formwork.

The Smart Concrete Wall, on the other hand, realised by NOWLab and BigRep in 2019, is the first "smart concrete wall" to be produced using 3D printing formwork on a large scale. The specific section of the hexagonal grid wall was designed using the logic of Arabic tiling, subjected to a parametric design process. This prototype demonstrates the great compositional freedom of the casting moulds thanks to the use of 3D printing, but it also highlights one of the most problematic aspects of this type of technique, namely the mould removal process, which must be taken into account in the design concept of the element itself in accordance with its geometry.

Another example of great application interest is the Dissolvable Formwork, created by Matthias Leschok in 2019. It involves the creation of 3D-printed formwork using water-soluble materials that can be simply washed away after the concrete has set, using only water and no additional chemical solvents. This project's parametric model was created in Grasshopper with the aim of creating a shape unattainable using traditional flexible moulding techniques.

The Cold Production prototype, also from ETH Zurich, is also interesting. It explores a waste-free production method for concrete using digitally modelled ice as a moulding material. The project explored spatial concrete grids and their stacking principles. The ice units have been created by pressing the ice into 3D printed modules, with the processing being carried out at a temperature of -10°C . The concrete was poured, cured and the next day the elements were placed outside to be removed by simply allowing the ice to melt, revealing the intricate concrete grid design.

This series of cases identifies two different approaches to indirect use of 3D printing for building in viscous materials: one relies on creating large moulds for casting parts of architecture in one piece, while another relies on printing a mould for mass production of minimal elements to build architecture. In both cases, however, 3D printing allows for much more complex and high-performance shapes than traditional

construction systems. In particular, the construction of small parts made through moulds produced by additive manufacturing is the field in which the FabLab POLIBA research group has tried to build an experiment that is described in this essay.

2 FUNCTIONAL FORM FINDING AND ALGORITHMIC SPACIAL TASSELLATION

The research described in this essay is the natural continuation of an experiment already carried out by the FabLab POLIBA research group with the Wood Beehive project, which was presented live with a prototype exhibited during the International Maker Faire in Rome in October 2022. It is based on finding the shape by writing spatial tessellation algorithms that interpret a specific performance requirement in the design process.

Tessellation is a tool for creating form using a digital and parametric modelling system and is based on the biological concept of cell growth, which is the basis for the creation of any organic form. Tessellation is a method of generating form through the creation of masses of smaller elements that can be repeated indefinitely. As such, there is no formal issue other than the generation of solids of all shapes and sizes. What makes it different is the dimensional relationship between the size of the component and the shape produced, both related to the scale of the building environment. In fact, with an extra dimension, it could be compared to what happens with the pixel/image ratio in raster digital files. A significant reduction in the modulus dimension tends to make the overall object more defined to the human eye, thus concealing its tessellated composition. On the contrary, increasing the size of the component module would lead to what is known as the 'pixelation effect'. In other words, the module would become more prominent in the composition. Tessellation is undoubtedly a very theoretical and experimental approach to form construction and has seen numerous applications in recent years, particularly in the design of demonstration pavilions.

Module+ is a pavilion built in Vietnam using approximately 2000 pieces in the shape of a Greek cross with mutual right-angled joints; it represents the simplest geometry for implementing spatial tessellation by working on a cubic-based geometric module.

The same principle applies to the "Reset Identity Pavilion" in Barcelona, built with small pieces of bamboo; the cube-shaped spatial network of very light pieces allows the construction of a roof covering a large span through a "low density" mass, thus demonstrating the constructive potential of three-dimensional mosaic compositions.

Starting from the cube-based geometry and considering the six equivalent pyramids built with the six faces and the centre of the solid, the Symbiosis studio produced a design solution by experimenting with it in the Plexus pavilion, an interactive 'plug and play' system made of two components; the combination of a series of nodes and connectors following the principles of spatial aggregation allowed the definition of a vast catalogue with more than a thousand different ways of constructing the perforated pavilion designed especially for exhibition events.

Modular spatial elements can be assembled in increasingly complex geometric arrangements; this is what ANYTHINGbutts is made up: tetrapods made from recycled and processed fine tobacco rods, giving life to an organic and monumental structure without using any kind of glue; it is designed to be assembled and arranged to create an infinite number of structural forms.

But a spatial tessellation can also be defined by the innovation of traditional systems such as the Japan Pavilion designed by architect Atsushi Kitagawara for the 2015 Expo in Milan. Inspired by ancient Satoyama village buildings, in which architecture found its balance with nature by making responsible use of natural resources, the studio combined traditional construction methods with the latest 3D programming technologies to create a wooden lattice structure made from felled trees without the use of nails or bolts.

Until we consider the extreme experimentation with all the variants of what is known as 'granular aggregation', which is based on the random arrangement of elements that are held together by shape and interlocking in the combined form. Like grains of sand, they can take on any shape that contains them, but they are able to preserve it without a container thanks to the geometric form of the mutually supporting elements. From Aggregate Wall to Zform, from Designed Particles to Adaptive Structure, there is a series of experiments abandoning precise geometric composition to adopt the scalar theme of mechanical friction for spatial aggregation.

Every tessellated construction system lives from the scalar relationship between its module and the composition. Being so small and infinitesimal compared to the constructed whole, the repeated element loses its own geometric visibility, becoming almost a constructive 'atom'. The consequence of this is that the

formal composition is independent of the system that constructs it. When it comes to architectural composition, then, the problem of form arises, as it always does in the designer's path, and for which he can choose the most diverse directions. The expressive potential of tessellated systems, however, is believed to lie in the ontological absence of form itself: capable of constructing any form, it prefers none. This is why the research took as its theme the project which, abandoning any a priori choice, constructs the so-called 'functional' or 'performance' form; In other words, the form that follows a predetermined function, designed with the primary objective of optimally responding to a specific request.

The 'Beehive' experiment proposes an algorithm based on spatial tessellation through the repetition of a truncated octahedron. The latter is known in geometry for being one of the few polyhedra that can tessellate space by repeating only itself, occupying the entire volume and therefore leaving no empty spaces.

The function of this algorithm is to tessellate the internal space of a Generic Solid through the repetition of a Truncated Octahedron, avoiding overlaps and gaps. The algorithm was created using the three-dimensional modelling software Blender, using a component called 'Sverchok' to design geometries using visual node programming.

The first step is to take an arbitrary three-dimensional solid, known as a generic, and a truncated octahedron, which is rotated so it lies on a hexagonal face at the base. In this position, the octahedron only grows symmetrically in the three directions of space when it is aggregated into a module called the 'minimum module', which consists of six elements. In order to obtain this aggregate, the algorithm takes the centroid of a hexagonal face of the octahedron, the face of adjacency with the nearest octahedron that forms the minimum module and draws a vector that connects the centre of the octahedron with the centroid of this face. Once this vector has been calculated, the algorithm decomposes it into the three directions of Cartesian space to obtain a precise distance between the minimum modules. This distance is used to define a vector field, i.e. a grid of vertices in space, which depends on the maximum size of the Generic Solid and the distance between the minimum modules. This vector field makes it possible to obtain the position of all the centres of the first octahedron for each minimum module that will make up the tessellation. The vector field is then replicated and shifted, considering the vector connecting the centre of the octahedron to the centroid of two adjacent faces between octahedra that form the minimum modulus, in order to identify the position of successive octahedra in the directions of modulus growth. The sum of these Vector Fields, known as the Vector Field of Minimum Modules, is then centred in the volume given by the maximum envelope of the given Generic Solid. Finally, the algorithm calculates how many of these points of the Vector Field of Minimum Modules are located within the generic solid and, for these points only, proceeds to copy and position all the octahedra so that the centre of each one corresponds to each individual vertex of the vector field within the volume of the given Generic Solid.

Once the tessellation algorithm had been defined, a functional objective was chosen as "the permanence of people in specific activities", with the need also to manage solar radiation in relation to the well-being of the structure's users. Thus, having chosen a specific location on Earth with its average annual radiation conditions, and having defined the permanence and movement of people in space, the overall shape of the architecture is created and submitted to the algorithm that tessellates it with the truncated octahedron module.

Fig. 1. (a) Truncated Octahedron Construction (b) Tessellation Algorithm (c) Composition

3 THE EARTH BEEHIVE PROTOTYPE

As for Wood Beehive, this time we challenge the construction of a prototype tessellating the space with octahedra by using raw earth. This applied research gains importance within a broader research field addressing the topic of updating forms built in natural viscous materials using new digital fabrication technologies. Two specific fields of application have been identified within this strand of research: the first aims to experiment with shapes built through the direct extrusion of the material with machines that move the extruder in different manners; the second, on the other hand, consider 3d printing an indirect technique to obtain complex moulds for subsequent casting of the mixtures. Obviously, this research typologies may have validity for a wide range of viscous materials ranging from cement to natural earth via slurries with geopolymeric binders. In our case, the experimentation focuses on the second research application typology using a natural earth mixture. The written algorithm, therefore, allows us to tessellate any shape we imagine. The experimentation has demonstrated its constructive applicability with a material such as raw earth in two summer schools organized in Casalincontrada with the collaboration of CED Terrae in Abruzzo, in an area strongly characterized by the presence of ancient earthen buildings.

3.1 The Molds Manufacturing

The investigation's first stage involved the manufacture of the molds for casting and subsequent compacting of the earth poured into the molds. For a shape such as a truncated octahedron ashlar, the main practical problem is to make a mold allowing the ashlar to unmold easily. Thus, we divided the outer surface of the geometry into two parts by sectioning it along some of the diagonals so that the mold could open without deforming the cast piece. After identifying the two surfaces, we selected a construction thickness consistent with the average strength of a 3d print in polylactic acid (PLA) chosen for this first prototyping. Finally, we opted for a top face open to allow the casting of the material: a face edge extruded along its normal configures a space for a piston modelled for compacting the mixture inside the mold. The two-part modelling of the ashlar mold was also designed to enable its additive manufacturing realization using Filament Deposition Modelling technology. Considering the use of the mold, fifteen molds of the base mold and about eight head molds were produced depending on the assumed drying times of the pieces. These molds were then used later for the first experimental production of the ashlars.

3.2 The Production of the Ashlars

The first experimental production of ashlars was carried out during the first session of the International Summer Academy Self Made Architecture V that took place from July 21 to 25, 2022 at the architect Gianfranco Conti's Atelier in Casalincontrada with the collaboration of the "Centro di Documentazione sulla terra cruda" (Documentation Center on Raw Earth) in Casalincontrada, Abruzzo. The mixture was worked in a muller and obtained by mixing two parts of a clay soil from the Abruzzo badlands, two parts of fine sand, one part of water and one part of chopped straw, all accounted in volumetric units. After mixing to obtain a homogeneous mixture, it was placed in covered containers to rest overnight. On the following day, we filled the fifteen molds by pouring the mixture and applying pressure for compaction through the plunger. After the first fifteen molds, we waited about three hours for the first stage of drying and took off the top part to reuse them to fill the other fifteen molds left to dry overnight along with the first ones. During the following two days, we re-employed the molds after unloading the pieces and proceeded, in the same way, producing, in three total work days, about ninety pieces. Once all pieces were produced in mid-July, they were then placed in a ventilated and covered outdoor area of the atelier to allow proper and complete drying for about two months from July to September.

Fig. 2. Process of making the ashlar. Steps and photographic images

3.3 The Assembly of the Prototype

The assembly of the prototype was carried out during the second session of the International Summer Academy Self Made Architecture V that took place from September 14-18, 2022 to coincide with the XXVIth Earth Festival held in Casalıncontrada, Abruzzo. The open space in front of 'Teresa's house', an ancient earthen artifact recovered and restored by Ced Terrae, acted as the construction site. The study carried out in the months preceding the construction site about the prototype to build highlighted a critical issue. After the study of the algorithmic tessellation, we used a plug-in to investigate the physical kinematics considering all the acting forces: all the volumes and weights were inferred from the material and a friction force was hypothesized. Considering these components, the system collapsed because of lateral pushes due to the shape of the ashlar, especially for the pieces without any support on the base face. Therefore, to allow the prototype to assemble, we produced hollow icosahedrons manufactured in advance and custom shaped on the prototype sculpture to solve this issue and provide base support for the suspended pieces. However, during the assembly phase, we verified that the behavior model virtualized by Blender was not correct after the creation of the compacted support platform for the construction of the prototype; thus, we decided to proceed with the construction without using the printed hollow supports and verified that the construction maintained its solidity until the final assembly phase. In the following days, a protective treatment was applied using linseed oil and the prototype to date stands solidly without even showing deterioration due to rainwater runoff.

Fig.3. Photo shoot on the laying of the ashlars

3.4 The Hollow Ashlar Variant

The design implementation of the Earth Beehive system was carried out by devising a particular variant of the truncated octahedron ashlar by emptying it through three extruded cylinders perpendicular to the hexagonal faces and passing through the centre of the ashlar. This new configuration of the ashlar makes it possible to create an internal mesh in the masonry mass during the assembly phase in which a material with structural characteristics of greater strength, including tensile strength, can be cast. With this approach, the entire construction would be endowed with greater compactness and strength and would provide the possibility of more complex forms without the risk of poorly anchored parts falling off due to friction. This implementation gives real potential to the system as a real construction technique. A modified mold was designed for the realization of the experimental ashlar. After the casting and drying phase, it allows a proper demolding of the inner cylinders first without compromising the integrity of the part. A specimen of this mold was made, and later, during the summer school in July, a model ashlar was also produced for this variant as a first phase of experimentation.

Fig. 4. The assembly system and hollow ashlar prototype

4 RAMMED EARTH PAVILION

The first design application at the building's architectural scale was proposed for the international competition "Rammed Earth Pavilion" organized by Buildner Architecture Competitions at the turn of 2022-2023. The competition was to design a pavilion measuring approximately 50 square meters using rammed earth, to be

used as an Earth Museum. A proposal based on the Earth Beehive prototype was developed by the FabLab Poliba research group. With the Black Rock Desert in Nevada as a backdrop, the idea was to create a space in the shape of a parallelepiped in which the functions could be located: on the ground floor there is a direct entrance to a space dedicated to the museum, with the possibility of going further up to have a view of the landscape. After defining the functional space, the Blender algorithm was used to tessellate the solid part of the design with truncated octahedrons bricks. The idea proposed was to produce the blocks themselves from desert earth, using reinforced moulds capable of creating blocks with mechanical strengths close to those of the Pisè technique. On the other hand, in order to make the whole building solid and buildable, the design provides for the use of internally excavated blocks to form the most overhanging parts of the structure. The museum would be created by importing different samples of earth from different parts of the world to make ashlars to be placed in the museum hall, testifying to the different raw earth traditions around the world. The final poetic idea was that as time passed, the earth would slowly dissolve until the pavilion disappeared completely, creating a circular architectural creation.

Fig. 5. Images of Rammed Earth Pavillion

5 CONCLUSION

The prototype presented represents the state of the art of a broader research, funded by a national research plan in Italy for the next three years, which proposes a study on the construction potential in civil engineering and architecture by combining additive manufacturing technology and viscous materials. The research will involve both the direct extrusion of viscous doughs using large-scale printing equipment and the indirect use of additive manufacturing, such as fused deposition modelling, to produce casting moulds for viscous doughs. Its main objective is to demonstrate how digital fabrication, and especially additive manufacturing, can be used for the creation of innovative building elements and systems with a dual purpose: i) developing a building systems for a circular economy in construction through the re-use of natural and waste materials with a zero-kilometer provenance; ii) proposing a system of building shapes that cannot be realized with traditional fabrication technologies using viscous dough.

One of the planned outcomes of the research is the realization of a larger prototype using a further development of the beehive system, using hollow blocks and casting a stronger material to make a reinforced net. This trial will be an opportunity for large-scale verification of the effectiveness of the construction system under investigation.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Project funded under the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP), Mission 4 Component 2 Investment 1.3 - Call for tender No. 341 of 15 March 2022 of Italian Ministry of University and Research funded by the European Union – NextGenerationEU.

Project code PE_00000004, Concession Decree No. D.D. Prot. N. 1551 of 11/10/2022 adopted by the Italian Ministry of University and Research, CUP: E63C22002130007 Project title 6.10 “The direct/indirect use of additive manufacturing in construction viscous mixtures.”